

FIBRE REINFORCEMENTS - PAST, PRESENT AND FUTURE

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ABSTRACT

The development of artificial fibres has been rapid and new types of fibres are continually being produced which can be used to reinforce all types of solids. The complexity and rigidity of organic molecules have been increased since their introduction less than fifty years ago so that they are now used to reinforce both elastomeric and harder resin systems. Another route to producing high performance organic fibres is to almost perfectly align the structure of simple polymers. The mechanical properties of glass fibres have been greatly exceeded by the development of carbon fibres made from acrylic precursor fibres and also pitch. The temperature range of fibres has recently been increased by the development of fine ceramic filaments capable of reinforcing metals and ceramics which promises to herald a new range of high temperature structural materials.

INTRODUCTION

A fibre is a long fine filament of matter with a diameter generally of the order of ten microns and an aspect ratio of length to diameter between a thousand and virtually infinity for continuous fibres.

Fibres are one of the most extraordinary forms of ordinary matter. They are often much stronger and stiffer than the same material in bulk form. All of nature, both in the animal and vegetable kingdoms, is based on fibrous structures and man has made use of natural fibres from prehistoric times. These uses were in clothing but also for some technical applications often in the form of cables, ropes and sails. However up until the second half of the twentieth century material development for structural end uses was

almost exclusively concerned with crystalline metals. Nature's example was ignored, even though, from earliest times the most widely used structural material, wood, was a supreme example of a naturally occurring composite material. That naturally occurring fibres were never seriously challenged by metals for use in apparel has been due to the same inherent qualities which has led to their use as reinforcements in composite materials. Fibres have remarkable specific properties so that for the same strength, for example, a steel filament would be three or four times heavier. The fineness of fibres allows them to be woven and draped into complex shapes, necessary in a garment but just as much exploited in filament winding. Cloth, woven or non-woven, is a means of converting a one dimensional filament into a two dimensional component. Many and perhaps most composite structures are essentially two dimensional whether they are carbon epoxy skins over a honey comb structure, a filament wound tube or a car body panel made by press moulding. Three dimensional weaving and needle punching are recent techniques of the textile industry which are also used for composites. Mechanical properties are but one aspect in the choice of a material and others such as thermal transfer or insulation behaviour, water retention and cost have determined the use of fibres in the past as they do today in composite materials.

Artificial fibres are only just one hundred years old and the earliest produced were based on the naturally occurring cellulose molecule. Towards the end of the nineteenth century workers in Great Britain and in France had found means of dissolving natural cellulose and then extruding it through holes to produce filaments. The first commercial exploitation of these regenerated fibres was in France where a patent to produce the earliest form of rayon was awarded to Count Hilaire de Chardonnet in 1888 [1]. This was the beginning of a revolution in fibre technology. The regenerated fibres did not exploit the total potential of the cellulose molecules as they were broken up to shorter lengths during the fibre manufacturing process. The cellulose was obtained from wood, usually spruce, made up of molecules containing about 1000 glucose residues but these were broken down to about a fifth of their original length in the manufacture of rayon [1, 2]. The intention of the first fibre producers was to produce an artificial silk for textile purposes however at the beginning of the twentieth century they found a major application in the carcasses of tyres for the developing automobile industry. Rayon fibres have evolved significantly over the years

and the descendants of these earliest artificial fibres are still to be found in some car tyres today.

ORGANIC FIBRES

It was not until around 1938 that the first truly synthetic organic fibres were produced from short molecules and continuous glass fibres were also commercially produced just before this date. Both the polyamide and glass fibres were developed in the U.S.A. respectively by E.I. du Pont de Nemours and what became Owens Corning. Almost simultaneously with the work of Carothers at Du Pont, polyamide was produced in Germany by I.G. Farben.

Since the production of the polyamide or nylon fibre other organic fibres have been produced and a trend towards the production of increasingly more rigid and complex molecules used in making the fibres is clearly discernible from Table 1. The aramid family of fibres made up of aromatic polyamides possesses remarkably high Young's moduli more than twenty times that of conventional polyamide fibres. The more rigid molecule confers not only higher mechanical properties but also better thermal resistance. This

TABLE 1
Molecular structure of several organic fibres showing the development of increasingly rigid molecules.

Fibre type	Repeat unit in the macromolecule	Maximum Elastic modulus GPa
Polyamide 6.6 Nylon 66	$- \text{NH} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} -$	5
Polyamide 6 nylon 6	$- \text{NH} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO} -$	4
Polyethylene terephthalate	$- \text{O} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{O} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 -$	18
Poly-meta-phenylenediamine -isophthalamide Nomex	$- \left[\text{N} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{H} \\ \diagdown \text{H} \end{array} \text{C}_6\text{H}_3 \text{N} \text{C} \begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \parallel \end{array} \right] -$	17
Poly (p-phenylene terephthalamide KEVLAR	$- \text{HN} - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 - \text{NNCO} - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 - \text{CO} -$	135

latter quality is a considerable advantage when these fibres are compared with other high modulus organic fibres made from simpler molecules such as polyethylene made by straightening out the molecular structure and exploiting the covalent bonds in the backbone of the molecule.

nylon and polyester (polyethylene terephthalate) fibres are extensively used for reinforcing rubber and these flexible composites are used in fan belts, hoses, flexible drives, moving walkways, tyres and other applications. Respectively, they account for 28 % and 48 % of the total synthetic fibre production. Both types of fibre are produced by melt spinning and are subsequently drawn to increase their Young's moduli. They are both semicrystalline with their molecular structures arranged in microfibrils consisting of crystalline blocks of regularly folded molecules linked by less well ordered molecules [3, 4]. Surrounding the microfibrils there are elongated but irregularly arranged molecules forming a mesamorphous phase. Crystallinity is often about 60 % in nylon fibres and somewhat less in the polyester fibres.

Neither fibre shows real elastic behaviour even at low strains and plastic deformation as well as creep occurs when the fibre, either by itself or in an elastomeric composite, is loaded. The properties required of these fibres, for example in a tyre, are high strength, dimensional stability, fatigue resistance, thermal stability and good bonding to the matrix. Tensile failure in both nylon and polyester fibres is similar involving slow crack growth from the surface, in a radial direction. The crack opens as the material ahead of the crack deforms plastically. A point is reached at which the crack becomes unstable and rapid failure occurs. The composite structures, for which organic fibres are used as reinforcements, are often subjected to dynamic loading and fatigue is a major concern. Many organic fibres can fail by a distinct failure process leading to a characteristic fracture morphology involving longitudinal crack growth which gradually reduces the load bearing fibre cross section [5]. The loading conditions which lead to this type of failure are unusual as a necessary criterion for fatigue failure is that the minimum cyclic load be nearly zero. Indeed it is possible to avoid fatigue by increasing the overall loading pattern on the fibre and if this does not raise it into a regime for creep failure, the fibre will no longer break [6]. The fatigue failure of these fibres seems to depend on the shear stresses set up between the intra and interfibrillar amorphous zones due to differences in compliances of these regions. These

shear stresses lead to the breakage of molecules and a local deterioration of the fibre. Eventually the fatigue crack appears and its development is influenced greatly by the anisotropic structure of the fibre [7] . It can be expected that fibres produced for structures subjected to severe cyclic loading will, in the future, have their molecular structures engineered so as to improve their fatigue lives. As is often the case the result is likely to be a compromise with other demands such as very high spinning speeds of up to possible 20 000 m/min which do not always lead to the best structure for fatigue behaviour. Other variations of nylon fibres may be seen such as the development of nylon 6.4 which has much improved shrinkage behaviour and should be of interest for elastomeric composites which require relatively high curing temperatures.

The aramid group of reinforced fibres, in the form of Kevlar has been available since 1972 and has been adopted for many composite structures. These fibres, which are made from a mesophase or liquid crystal solution of the polymer in concentrated sulphuric acid, have remarkable tensile properties. In air they are five times as strong as steel for the same weight and this difference rises to thirty times when they are used in water, because of their low density. The highly anisotropic structure of aramid fibres results, however, in them being weak in all other directions [8, 9] . For this reason the fibres are not used in primary loading structures subjected to compressive forces. The great tenacity of the aramid fibres means that they absorb much more energy than more brittle fibres when broken. For this reason aramids are finding increasing use as an energy absorbing material either in hybrid composites or for example in body armour. These aramid fibres are well accepted by the composite community and with the number of suppliers increasing they should find wider markets. Future trends will probably see increases in Young's modulus and Du Pont has announced the development of Kevlar 149 with a modulus of 165 GPa.

The Technora fibre, formally known as HM-50, from Teijein fits into the aramid family although it is not produced from a mesophase. It has an intermediate modulus and seems destined for reinforcing rubber.

An alternative approach to producing high modulus organic fibres is to use simple polymers and to arrange during their manufacture that the molecular structure be straightened out. In this way maximum use is made of the strong covalent bonds in the backbone of the molecule. A theoretical

analysis of the rigidity which is potentially possible with such a structure gives a value of around 240 GPa [10]. Two main manufacturing approaches exist for producing this type of fibre. The sol-gel approach, in which the polymer is dissolved in a solvent and then spun, is at present the only technique yielding commercially available fibres [11]. High modulus polyethylene fibres produced in Holland by DSM and Allied in the U.S.A. have properties rivalling those of the aramid fibres with a lower specific gravity of 0.97. These fibres which have only recently appeared will probably find uses in composites for sports goods. They are limited in temperature to a maximum of 120°C and suffer from creep. The other manufacturing route is to draw directly from the melt. This is potentially a cheaper technique but the Young's moduli of the fibres produced are not so high [12, 13]. It is claimed that cross linking by radiation of these fibres solves the creep problem [14].

FIBRES PRODUCED ON A SUBSTRATE

The first fibre produced with a much increased Young's modulus compared to glass fibres was the boron fibre made by a chemical vapour deposition technique onto a substrate which was a tungsten wire. Boron, the fifth element in the Periodic table, is the lightest element with which it was found practical to make fibres. The first boron fibres were produced in the U.S.A. and then in France at the beginning of the 1960 s. They had remarkable properties with a Young's modulus exceeding 400 GPa and quite extraordinary strength in compression. This latter quality was enhanced by their large diameter of 140 μm [15]. The manufacturing technique requires that each fibre be made separately and at a low speed. As a consequence these fibres are, and seem destined to remain, extremely expensive. Most of the applications originally foreseen for boron fibres have been taken over by carbon fibres. Boron fibres did prove to be a good reinforcement for light alloys particularly when the fibre was protected by a coating of SiC or B_4C . The American space shuttle is composed of a skeleton made up of more than 200 tubes in boron fibre reinforced aluminium but the very high cost of the fibre has restricted any wider use.

Silicon carbide fibres produced by a similar technique to that used to make boron fibres, remain a possible reinforcement for metal matrix composites. These fibres are based on materials which are readily available

and the substrate can either be tungsten wire or a carbon filament, which is cheaper. These SiC fibres have very good mechanical properties with a Young's modulus of 412 GPa and can be used at high temperatures around 1000°C, although reactions between the fibres and the matrix they are reinforcing may limit their temperature range in a particular system [16]. This production route for making fibres remains however very expensive and it is difficult to imagine a major development of this type of fibre.

CARBON FIBRES

Carbon fibres made by carbonizing cotton fibres were the first filaments used in Edison's incandescent electric lamps but they were extremely brittle and rapidly replaced by tungsten wire. Many fibres can be converted into carbon fibres, the basic requirement being that the precursor fibre carbonizes rather than melts when heated [17]. The route adopted in the U.S.A. in the 1950s and early 1960s to producing fibres from the next lightest element after boron was to use rayon regenerated fibres. This proved a slow process which did not yield spectacular results. The approach taken in Great Britain and Japan was to use polyacrylonitrile (PAN) fibres as precursors for making carbon fibres. This route based on a modified form of acrylic textile fibres was to prove successful and is the technique used today to make by far the greatest number of carbon fibres. The properties of carbon fibres made by this route depend on the temperature of pyrolysis used so that it is possible to produce a family of carbon fibres with different structures [18, 19]. Table 2 shows the properties of a range of fibres used in composite materials. The values given for the carbon fibres are typical however there exists a considerable range of properties for these fibres. In about ten years the strain to failure of commercially available carbon fibres has almost doubled going from 1% to 1.8% and fibre producers are in a position to produce fibres with strains to failure of 2.2%. This improvement has been brought about through optimizing the structure and quality of the precursor as well as the conditions of pyrolysis and a reduction in fibre diameter to 5 μm . Further increases in strain to failure would seem possible however the resins which are available today do not allow the improvements in fibre properties to be fully exploited and future improvements may wait for the developments of new resins.

TABLE 2
Comparison of fibre properties

Fibre type	Specific Gravity	Young's Modulus E GPa	Strength σ GPa	Strain to failure %	Specific Strength σ/p	Specific Modulus E/p	Diameter μm	Highest Utilisable $^{\circ}\text{C}$ temp.
E Glass	2.5-2.6	69-72	1.7-3.5	3	1.18	27.6	5-25	350
S Glass	2.48	85	4.8	5.3	1.94	24.3	5-15	300
Boron	2.4-2.60	365-440	2.3-2.8	1.0	0.88-1.08	140-191	33-140	2000
Carbon H.M.	1.96	517	1.86	0.38	0.95	164	8-4	600
Carbon H.S.	1.8	295	5.6	1.8	3-11	164	5.5	500
Al ₂ O ₃ Dupont	3.95	379	1.38-2.1	0.4	0-46	96	20	1000
Nicalon SiC	2.8	45-480	0.3-4.9	0.6	0.47	26	10-12	1300
Avco SiC	2.7-3.3	427	3.4-4.0	1	1.1	116	140	
Al ₂ O ₃	3.25	210	1.8	1.17	0.55	64.6	17	1250
Tyranno UBE	2.4	120	2.5	2.2	1.04	50	1	1300
Nextel-3M	2.5	152	1.72	1.95	0.8	156	13	1200
Al ₂ O ₃ (ICI)	3.3	300	2	1.5	0.8	120	3	1000
SiO ₂	2.2-2.5	75	5.9	1.5-1.8	2.3-2.7	28.8-32	1-3	1100
Nylon 66	1.2	< 5	1	20	0.8	4.1	25	150
Polyester	1.38	< 18	0.8	15	0.6	13	25	150
Kevlar 49	1.45	135	3	8.1	2.1	93	12	250
Technova-HM50	1.39	75	3	4.3	2.1	54	12	250
Spectra 900	0.97	117	3	3.5	3.1	120	38	120

Carbon fibres made from PAN precursors have an assured market in the aerospace industry. Their cost however prohibits their wider use in other large volume industries such as in the automobile industry. Considerable effort has been put into making carbon fibres from pitch, the residue left after the refining of oil or coal. The starting product, pitch, is readily and cheaply available however the considerable problems of converting it into fibres increases the overall cost of this route which has so far produced useful fibres of very high moduli but no commercially available high strength fibres. There are plans however by several Japanese companies such as Mitsubishi Chemicals to begin commercial production of carbon fibres made from coal pitch at the end of 1987. It is probable that most of these fibres are not destined for the aerospace industry but rather for the sports and leisure fields and possibly eventually bigger volume markets such as the automobile industry. Some observers put off the use of carbon fibres in the automobile industry until the turn of the century [20].

CERAMIC FIBRES

Fine ceramics fibres are not yet ten years old. The FP fibre from Du Pont de Nemours which became commercially available around 1979 is a pure α -alumina continuous fibre [21]. It was produced for the reinforcement of metals. The fibres are made by blending the alumina in powder form with other compounds to form a mixture which can be spun. Filaments are then extruded through spinnerets drawn and then heated in air to 1300°C to produce the α -alumina fibres.

The fibre has a high Young's modulus but suffers from being extremely brittle due to the large grain size of the α -alumina. This restricts its use and prevents it being woven. It has a diameter of 15 to 20 μm and can stand temperatures up to 1000°C.

The development in the early 1980's of the Nicalon fibre by Nippon Carbon based on the work of Yajima and his colleagues marked the beginning of a new type of fibre [22]. The Nicalon fibre is composed of about 70% SiC with the rest made up of excess silicon and oxygen in the form of silica, and free carbon [23]. This fibre with a diameter of 12 to 15 μm is made from a polycarbosilane precursor which is pyrolysed in an analogous fashion to the manufacture of carbon fibres made from PAN. The Nicalon fibre can be used to reinforce both metals and ceramics such as SiC and can

withstand temperatures up to 1000°C. Above this temperature the fibre is found to creep and the oxygen and free carbon in its structure reacts producing a slow deterioration of properties [24, 25]. The Nicalon fibre is also finding use because of its dielectric properties which can be modified so as to make resin matrix composites which are more or less transparent to microwave radiation.

A similar route to that taken to produce the Nicalon fibre is used by UBE industries in Japan to produce the Tyrano fibre which also contains titanium. The fibre is amorphous and its manufacturer claims that the fibre can be used up to 1300°C with no change in structure [26]. Preliminary studies on the Tyrano fibre heated in air to 1300°C indicate however that a reaction does take place at the surface which will most probably affect its mechanical properties [27].

Other fibres based on alumina have recently been produced. The alumina fibre produced by Sumitomo is made by first using an organo aluminium compound which is polymerized and dissolved in an organic solvent together with a silicon containing compound. The viscous mix which is produced is spun and the precursor fibres which are produced are fired in air to a temperature higher than 1000°C. The resulting fibre consists about 85 % γ or η alumina and 15 % silica. These fibres which have diameters of around 15 μm have a considerably lower Young's modulus than does the FP fibre but have the useful quality of being much more easy to handle and can be woven. The fibre is limited in use to temperatures up to about 1000°C at which temperatures the fibre creeps. Between 1100°C and 1150°C the fibre undergoes a sudden transformation and loses much of its strength and modulus [28].

The Safil alumina fibre produced by ICI was originally intended as a refractory insulating fibre. Later it was realized that this chopped fibre with a fine diameter of only 3 μm was a potentially useful reinforcing fibre for metals . The fibre has been further developed and a semi continuous variety, Safimax, is now available. The fibre is described as containing 96 % Al_2O_3 mainly in the delta phase with 4 % SiO_2 [29].

Other manufacturers produce continuous ceramic fibres such as 3-M's Nextel fibre and the list is likely to grow longer in the next few years. The prospect of reinforcing ceramics by fibres and thereby making them tougher is exciting as it promises to create a new family of structural

materials capable of withstanding high temperatures in oxydizing atmospheres. The development of this new class of fibre is being stimulated by the need for materials capable of withstanding temperatures above 1200°C for use in the next generations of space planes and shuttles. These fibres should also find use in diesel engines and possibly brake linings.

Other forms of short ceramic fibres and whiskers are being produced and although it is not the intention to treat this form of reinforcement in great detail here they should be mentioned as a potentially important form of reinforcement for metals. The reinforcement of light alloys by these short filaments was considered at the beginning of composite development [30] Variability in properties and dimensions as well as high cost and the lack of suitable applications prevented their progress. However today a range of new short filaments with more controlled properties and the promise of being affordable are appearing [31] . Their use for such applications as reinforcing aluminium connecting rods is attracting great interest and they may provide the means of increasing considerably the Young's Moduli of conventional light alloys.

CONCLUSION

The development of synthetic fibres since their beginning fifty years ago has been remarkable and even economic crises have not slowed their progress. Indeed in many ways advances in fibre technology has been stimulated by economic difficulties and energy shortages as they are seen, when used in composites, as a means of overcoming these problems. Fibres now exist to reinforce all classes of solids. Their number and varieties are continually increasing as are their properties. The development of organic fibres rapidly changed the everyday life of the man in the street. The development of advanced fibres has already revolutionized the aerospace industry and they are set to bring profound changes to industry as a whole.

REFERENCES

1. Moncrieff, R.W., Man-Made Fibres. Butterworth 6th Ed. 1979.
2. Morton, W.E. and Hearle, J.W.S., Physical Properties of Textile Fibres. Heinemann 2nd Ed. London, 1975.
3. Prevorsek, D.C., Kwon, Y.D., and Sharma, R.K., Structure and Properties of Nylon 6 and PET Fibres : the Effects of Crystallite Dimensions. J. Mat. Sci., 12, 1977, p. 2310.

4. Oudet, Ch., Bunsell, A.R., Hagege, R., and Sotton, M., Structural Changes in Polyester Fibres during Fatigue. J. App. Pol. Sci. 29, 1984, p. 4363.
5. Bunsell, A.R., and Hearle, J.W.S., The Fatigue of Synthetic Polymeric Fibres. J. App. Polymer. Sci. 18, 1974, p. 267.
6. Oudet, Ch., and Bunsell, A.R., Loading Criteria for the Fatigue Failure of Polyamide 66 Fibres. J. Mat. Sci. Letters, 3, 1984, p. 295.
7. Veve, J. Ch., Bunsell, A.R., and Baillie, C., Fatigue Failure and
7. Veve, J. Ch., Bunsell, A.R., and Baillie, C., Fatigue Failure and Associated Molecular Changes in Polyester Fibres under Cyclic Loading. To be published.
8. Greenwood, J.H., and Rose, P.G., Compressive behaviour of Kevlar-49 Fibres and Composites. J. Mat. Sci. 9, 1974, p. 1809.
9. Lafitte, M.H., Bunsell, A.R., and Mudry, F., Comportement en Torsion des Fibres de Kevlar 29. Colloques Int. CNRS 319- Comportement Plastique des Solides Anisotropes, 1985, p. 289.
10. Harris, B., and Bunsell, A.R., Structure and Properties of Engineering Materials. Pub. Longman, London, 1977.
11. Kalb, B., and Pennings, A.J., Maximum Strength and Drawing Mechanism of Hot drawn high Molecular weight Polyethylene. J. Mat. Sci., 15, 1980, p. 2229.
12. Bashir, Z., Odell, J.A., and Keller A., High Modulus Filaments of Polyethylene with Lamellar Structure by Melt Processing ; the Role of the high Molecular weight Component. J. Mat. Sci. 19, 1984, p. 3713.
13. Wilding, M.A., and Ward, I.M., Creep and Stress Relaxation in Ultra High Modulus Linear Polyethylene. J. Mat. Sci., 19, 1984, p. 629.
14. Ward, I.M., High Modulus Flexible Polymers and their Composites. New Materials 86, Japan, Osaka, 1986, p. 281.
15. Wawner, F.E., Boron Filaments. (ch. 10). Modern Composite Materials. Ed. L. Broutman and R. Krock, Addison-Wesley Pub. Co. Reading, Mass 1967, 244.
16. Wawner, F.E., Boron and Silicon Carbide Fibres. Ch.8 Fibre Reinforcement for Composite Materials. Ed. A.R. Bunsell. Pub. Elsevier Amsterdam. To be published, 1987.
17. Sittig, M., Carbon and Graphite Fibres : Manufacture and Applications. Noyes Dates Co., N.J., 1980.
18. Fitzer, E., and Heine, M., Carbon Fibre Manufacture and Surface Treatment. Fibre Reinforcements for Composite Materials. Ed. A.R. Bunsell Pub. Elsevier, Amsterdam. To be published.
19. Oberlin, A., and Guigon, M., The Structure of Carbon Fibres. Ed. A.R. Bunsell. Pub. Elsevier, Amsterdam. To be published.
20. Morita, Ken-ichi., Carbon Fibres used in high Performance Composites. New Materials 86 Japan, Osaka, 1986, p. 291.
21. Dhingra, A.K., Alumina Fibre FP. Phil. Trans. R. Soc., London, A294, 1980, p. 411.
22. Yajima, S., Okamura, K., Hayashi, J., and Omori, M., Synthesis of Continuous SiC Fibres with high Tensile Strength. J. Am. Ceram. Soc., 59, 1976, p. 324.

23. Simon, G., and Bunsell, A.R., Mechanical and Structural Characterisation of the NICALON Silicon Carbide Fibre. J. Mat. Sci., 19, 1984, p. 3649.
24. Simon, G., and Bunsell, A.R., Creep Behaviour and Structural Characterization at high Temperature of NICALON SiC Fibres. J. Mat. Sci., 19, (1984), p. 3658.
25. Bunsell, A.R., and Simon, G., Mechanical and Structural Characterisation of NICALON SiC Fibres up to 1300°C. Composite Sci. and Tech., 27, (1986), p. 157.
26. UBE Industries (Fd. New Materials in Ube Industrie. Company documents, 1986.
27. Aubin, C., and Bunsell, A.R., Unpublished results.
28. Liesnewski, Ch., and Bunsell, A.R., Unpublished results.
29. ICI Data.
30. Shaffer, T.B., Whiskers : their growth and Properties. Modern Composite Materials. Ed. L.J. Broutman and R.H. Kroch. Addison Wesley Pub. Co. Reading Mass, 1967.
31. Akyama, M., Ceramic Fibres. Fibre Reinforcements for Composite Materials. Ed. A.R. Bunsell Elsevier to be published, 1987.